

Production System Preliminary Design of Edible-Biodegradable Plastic Sachet and Various Value Added Byproducts from Papaya (*Caricae papaya*) Using Biorefinery

Ghiffary Rifqialdi^{1*}, Andi Afif Naufaldi¹, Adam Muhammad Syach¹, Rian Fiqraini¹

¹ Bioengineering Department, School of Life Science and Technology, Institut Teknologi Bandung, Jl. Ganesha No. 10, Bandung, 40312, Indonesia

*e-mail: ghiffaryr@students.itb.ac.id

Abstract—Plastic is one of the most practical storage that is used by most of Indonesian. However, it has negative effects on the environment. Due to this problem, researches has been made. One of the solution is edible-biodegradable plastic. Natural material is used so that it is environmental friendly and edible. The aim of this research is to apply biorefinery concept to make a sustainable edible-biodegradable plastic production system. Through this biorefinery concept, solid waste is processed to produce high protein and lipid biomass by bioconversion process with black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*). Gross profit margin, process flow diagram, and mass balance analysis were used in this research. The use of biorefinery concept results in a high amount of Gross Profit Margin (GPM). From 60,377 kg of papaya, it produces 3 million sheet of circle-shaped edible-biodegradable plastic sachet with 15 cm diameter, 5,132 kg of papaya seeds, 978 kg of papaya peel antioxidant powder, 5,484 kg of black soldier fly larvae (BSFL), 21,935 kg of liquid fertilizer, and 27,418 kg of organic compost. It turns out, with this biorefinery concept, a GPM of 10.279 is acquired, surpassing the conventional production system that has a GPM of 8.2—increasing profit by 44%.

Keywords—biorefinery; black soldier fly; edible-biodegradable plastic; papaya peel antioxidant powder

I. INTRODUCTION

Plastic usage is something that cannot be avoided in Indonesians' lives. Due to its diverse function, plastic is commonly used, even from domestic uses to industrial uses. Plastic is a cheap, easy to get, not poisonous, stable, microbe resistant, light, easy to make, and reusable material—making it a good storage material. However, despite its many function, it takes a long time for plastic to be degraded in the soil [1]. According to [2], Indonesia is the second biggest plastic waste producer—producing about 187.2 tons of plastic waste to the sea. This would have a negative impact for progressing sustainable environment.

Researches have been conducted to solve this problem. One of them is the substitution of synthetic plastic to biodegradable plastic. Central Bureau of Statistic Indonesia reported papaya production in Indonesia decreases about 3.23% from 2016 to 2017 [3]. Nevertheless, the production is still on a good condition, about 953,853 tons on 2017. Papaya can also be used as a material to produce high quality commodity, such as edible-biodegradable plastic. With its nutraceutical characteristic [4], papaya pulp as the ingredient of edible-biodegradable plastic can improve food quality. High pectin content on papaya can be utilized as a matrix that

strengthen the plastic itself [5]. Papaya can be the solution to solve plastic waste problems.

A papaya (*Caricae papaya*) fruit consists of 8.5% seed, 12% peel, and 79.5% fruit flesh [6]. Papaya peel is thrown away in conventional uses. In contrast, with the implementation of biorefinery concept, papaya peel will be processed to be high quality goods. Papaya peel is rich in vitamin and amino acid, β -karoten, lycopene, and polyphenol [7]. With its high content of antioxidant, 10 g of papaya peel can produce $15.18 \pm 0.007 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ with 13.5% [8] using acetone 90% extraction method. Solid waste from antioxidant production can be used as feed for black soldier fly larvae (*Hermetia illucens*). These larvae are usually used as a healthy and high protein food for livestock. Black soldier fly larva (BSFL) can prevent disease transmission to its predator [9]. BSFL also has high content of fat, about 27–37 wt%, depends on its substrate content [10], [11]. With its high protein and fat content, BSFL can be used as alternative feed for livestock. Larvae will be harvested when it is on prepupae stage due to high dry mass [12]. Cultivation is done from eggs hatching and harvested on its prepupae stage. The rest of solid waste that is not consumed by the BSFL will be utilized as organic compost and liquid fertilizer.

The goal of this research is to compare gross profit margin, process flow diagram, and mass balance between

conventional production system and biorefinery—based production system. By using biorefinery concept, solid waste can be processed to be high quality goods. The use of BSFL can bring not only financial advantages, but also the effort to achieve the sustainable environment.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Analysis Properties of Edible-Biodegradable Plastic Sachets from Papaya

The quality potential of edible-biodegradable plastic sachets from papaya is analyzed based on literature. The function of additional compounds will be explained in the discussion.

B. Design of Process Flow Diagram

Process Flow Diagram is a diagram describing production system flow consisting of interconnected operating units. The diagram for edible-biodegradable plastic sachets with the biorefinery application scheme will be explained in more detail.

C. Mass Balance Analysis

Mass balance analysis is used to show the flow of raw materials and the determination of product results in a particular scheme process. This method is used to simulate the production process of edible-biodegradable plastic sachets and various byproducts.

D. Economic Analysis

Gross profit margin is a method used to analyze the economic value of a production system. Analyzing is based on the comparison of the selling price of the product to the raw material used. The equation used is as follows

$$GPM = (\sum TPP - \sum TRMP) / \sum TRMP \quad (1)$$

Where TPP is total product price and TRMP is total raw material price. This analysis is used to determine the production flow that can increase sales value by comparing each process. Conventional production flow (red line) and biorefinery concept (red and black line) is shown in Figure 1. Following are the assumptions used in this study.

TABLE I. THE ASSUMPTION FOR GPM AND MASS BALANCE ANALYSIS

Raw Materials				
Material	Amount	Unit	Price (each unit)	Total Price (Rupiah)
Papaya	60,377	kg	8,000	483,016,000
Defatted soy protein	24,000	kg	28,000	672,000,000
Gelatin	18,000	kg	14,000	252,000,000
Starch	12,000	kg	18,000	216,000,000
Glycerol	18,000	kg	25,000	450,000,000
Distilled water	33,502	kg	1,000	33,502,000
Acetone 70%	18,113	kg	14,000	253,582,000
Tofu waste	15,668	kg	1,000	15,668,000
BSF eggs	11	kg	10,000	110,000
Products				
Product	Amount	Unit	Price (each unit)	Total Price (Rupiah)
Edible-biodegradable plastic sachet	3,000,000	pcs	6,000	18,000,000,000
Papaya seed	5,132	kg	210,000	1,077,720,000
Antioxidant powder	978	kg	6,062,000	5,928,636,000
BSFL biomass	5,484	kg	100,000	548,400,000
Liquid fertilizer	21,935	kg	56,000	1,228,360,000
Organic compost	27,418	kg	500	13,709,000

Fig. 1. Production scheme

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Properties of Edible-Biodegradable Plastic Sachet from Papaya

Method of making plastic film from papaya refer to [13]. The main material used in his research was papaya puree. Additional compound added to the main material. Some of these materials are distilled water, starch, glycerol, defatted soy protein, and gelatin.

Starch used as an alternative to synthetic polymers. Adding starch to film can cause fragility. However, the fragility of plastic can be controlled by plasticizers. Glycerol is one of the compounds that can be used as a plasticizer for film making [14].

Defatted soy protein generally contains 40% to 60% of soy protein with an oil content of less than 1% [15]. It can improve the biodegradable properties of plastic so that it is well used as a mixture material [16]. By its nature, it is able to increase the ability of water vapor to pass through plastic better than hydrophilic synthetic polymers [17], [18].

Gelatin was used to increase transparency of film. Besides that, gelatin increases the tensile strength and excellent barrier to oxygen—carbon dioxide [19]. It also acts as thickening agent, gelling agent, stabilizer, and emulsifier [20].

The right combination of additional compound can increase plastic quality. Combination of 8 g papaya puree, 100 mL distilled water, 2 g starch, 3 g glycerol, 3 g gelatin, and 4 g defatted soy protein was found to be the best combination compared to other papaya film [13]. Changing properties are increased tensile strength, increased thickness, increased water vapor permeability, reduced oxygen permeability, reduced carbon dioxide permeability, increased tear resistance, and increased sealing strength, but reduced the percentage of elongation

at break ability, increased water contact angle, and increased water solubility. With that combination, papaya film material can be made in circle-shape with a diameter of 15 cm and thickness of $119.33 \pm 2.08 \mu\text{m}$.

B. Process Flow Diagram

In this preliminary production design, Figure 2 explain conventional (red line) and biorefinery process (red and black line). Conventional process result in edible-biodegradable plastic and papaya seed. It start from separating papaya fruit (S-101) to papaya flesh (S-102), seed (S-113) and peel (S-114). Papaya flesh is grinded into puree. Then, add papaya puree (S-103) : distilled water (S-104) : starch (S-105) with weight composition 8 : 100 : 2 to mixer at 75°C for 30 minutes. After film base solution mixed, glycerol (S-107) : gelatin (S-108) : defatted soy protein (S-109) in amount of 3 : 3 : 4 dissolved to mixer for 30 minutes. Mixed solution (S-110) transferred to $120 \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$ thickness petri dishes each 100 mL mixture. Each petri dish, incubated in convection oven at 40°C and 23% humidity for 18 hours. Further drying, uses silica gel industrial desiccant dehumidifier at 25°C for 48 hour to reduce water content. After 66 hours incubated, every two plastic material (S-112) were joined each other. Plastic sealing machine were used to make circle-shaped edible-biodegradable plastic sachet with 15 cm diameter (S-113).

To apply biorefinery concept, papaya peel waste (S-115) were processed (black line). In processing antioxidant extract, papaya peel were cut into 1 cm^2 and milled using miller at 3873 rpm. Furthermore, papaya peel powder was extracted with acetone 70% (S-117) with ratio of 100 : 250 using the soxhlet method for 60 minutes to obtain a crude extract of antioxidant. The crude extract (S-119) concentrated using a rotary evaporator at 45°C to vaporize the remaining solvents. Then, dry it (S-120) with an oven at 45°C overnight to form an antioxidant powder.

Fig. 2. Process Flow Diagram of Production Scheme

BSFL cultivation process begins with the mixing papaya peel solid waste (S-122), tofu waste (S-123), and distilled water (S-124). The feed mixture is transferred into the biomass multiplication tank and added with BSF eggs (S-125) as the bioconversion agent. After going through the bioconversion process for 20–54 days, the BSFL biomass is in the prepupae phase and harvested (S-127). Because in it phase, BSFL has the highest mass compared to other phases. Residue in the biomass multiplication tank is further separated to obtain liquid fertilizer (S-128) and organic compost (S-129).

C. Mass Balance Analysis

In Figure 3 mass balance analysis begins with separation of 60,377 kg total weight of mature papaya fruits to produce 48,000 kg of papaya pulp, 7,245 kg of papaya skin, and 5,433 kg of seeds [6]. To produce 3 million pieces of circle-shaped edible-biodegradable plastic sachet with 15 cm diameter, 48,000 kg of papaya puree, 600 kg of distilled water, 24,000 kg of defatted soy protein, 18,000 kg of gelatin, 12,000 kg of starch, and 18,000 kg of glycerol were used. Plastic weight

calculation is not required in this case because plastic selling price determined based on plastic area.

In extracting antioxidants, it takes 18,113 kg of acetone 70% to extract 7,245 kg of papaya peel. With yields of 13.5% [8], we obtained 978 kg of papaya peel antioxidant powder. There are 6,267 kg of papaya peel solid waste remaining extraction. The waste is used in further processing for BSFL feed production.

A total of 6,267 kg of papaya solid waste is mixed with 15,668 kg of tofu waste before being transferred to the biomass multiplication tank to increase the protein content of feed. To maximize larval cultivation, regulated feed moisture by adding 32,902 kg of distilled water to obtain 60% moisture [21] to produce 54,837 kg of BSF (Black Soldier Fly) feed. Based on research conducted by Agrotechnology and Bioproduct Department at SITH ITB, the BSFL (Black Soldier Fly Larvae) will convert 10% of feed into high protein biomass, 40% liquid fertilizer, and 50% into compost. After harvesting, it will be obtained 5,484 kg BSFL in prepupae form, 21,935 kg of liquid fertilizer, and 27,418 kg of organic compost.

Fig. 3. Mass Balance Diagram

D. Gross Profit Margin

GPM analysis on the conventional and biorefinery system showed that the biorefinery system production has larger value of 10.279 compared to 8.2 from conventional system. Assumptions used in the GPM calculation is presented in Table I. The larger value of GPM in biorefinery system reflects that the application of biorefinery system can add much economic value for the edible-biodegradable plastic processing industry. The biorefinery production system can produce four additional bioproducts which greatly increase the revenue. The application of biorefinery concept can increase the profit of edible-biodegradable plastic processing process increased by 44%.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on GPM analysis result, application of the biorefinery concept to the production system of edible-biodegradable plastics from papaya more profitable than conventional system. Mass balance analysis shows a biorefinery integrated production system produces 3 million pieces of circle-shaped edible-biodegradable plastic sachet with 15 cm diameter, 5,132 kg papaya seeds, 978 kg papaya peel antioxidant powder, 5,484 kg BSF biomass, 21,935 kg liquid fertilizer, and 27,418 kg organic compost. The process flow diagram in this study shown alternative process more sustainable economically and environmentally.

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